

THE SCOURGE OF COVID-19 AND SECURITY CHALLENGES IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The paper examined the scourge of coronavirus (COVID-19) and its challenges to Nigeria's security. This paper is guided by the assumptions of Ichiro Kawachi, Bruce Kennedy and Richard Wilkinson's social disorganization approach, developed in 1999. The study adopted an online survey design that required software application designed specifically for smart phones and tablet personal computers. A sample size of 400 was determined using Taro Yamen's scientific formula. Population of the study consisted social media users who were volunteers. The study adopted quantitative method of data analysis and primary data was collected using structured questionnaire designed on strata basis, comprising; Agreed, Strongly Agreed, Undecided, Disagreed and Strongly Disagreed format. The instrument was circulated on social media platforms to get first-hand information from participants. Out of 400 soft copies of questionnaire circulated online, only 302 were filled and submitted and same was used for data presentation and analysis. Data was presented and analyzed descriptively using frequency distribution tables and simple percentage. The findings show that COVID-19 has largely shifted government focus away from the existing insecurity challenges in Nigeria like Boko Haram, banditry, farmers-herdsmen conflict and other social unrest like police brutality to tackling the virus which had devastating effects on the security architecture of the nation. The study recommends a strategic security approach that involves managing COVID-19 and addressing security issues simultaneously. The security agencies should not be ignored simply because of the presence of COVID-19; such inaction will create more devastating effects than COVID-19.

Keywords: Scourge, COVID-19, Security, Challenges

INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization (WHO, 2020), observed the alarming severity of coronavirus spread in many countries, on March 11, 2020, they announced that it is now a global pandemic. The new Coronavirus (COVID-19) was first reported in Wuhan city of China in December, 2019. Since then, it has become a huge threat to lives, economic and social wellbeing of all citizens of the world. Many countries across the global community faced and some are still facing unprecedented challenges from COVID-19 pandemic (United Nations Development Programme, 2020) and Nigeria is not an exemption to the global impact of Coronavirus outbreak (Olisah, 2020). Nigeria has been facing multiple security challenges that COVID-19 met on ground, the challenges include; Boko Haram, farmers-herdsmen conflict, banditry, police brutality, corruption, armed robbery, human rights violations and theft, all of which had made the impact of COVID-19 very devastating.

As the world tries to counter the pandemic, Nigeria continues its battle against insurgent groups threatening the stability and political integrity of Africa's most populous state (Kishor, 2020). The advent of the pandemic has largely shifted focus away from the security challenges (Op-Ed Contributor, 2020). The areas in Northern Nigeria already affected by the violent conflicts are particularly vulnerable. Boko Haram groups have stepped up its attacks as the number of cases in Borno State grows (Campbell, 2020). These attacks combined with other battles between farmers and herders and increasing number of banditry in the northwest have displaced hundreds of thousands of people. Recently, United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR, 2019) reported that there are 70.8 million Internally Displaced Persons (IDP) globally and Nigeria accounts for the highest number of displaced persons within the African region and one of the global highest rates (Roberts, 2020 and Onubugu, 2020).

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The lockdown measures increased the demand for food in IDP camps, and the conditions in these camps made it challenging, if not impossible, for people to protect themselves from the virus. As the lockdowns and other security issues continue, many Nigerians have little confidence that the attitude of the security forces would improve soon. Agomuo (2020) pointed out that COVID-19 has both health and security challenges. He went further to maintain that before the advent of COVID-19 there have been a state of insecurity in Nigeria occasioned by criminality and acts of lawlessness. COVID-19 has brought about economic downturn and pervasive insecurity. Gambhir (No Date) also observed that the global pandemic has brought an additional dimension to security issues. He also added that COVID-19 has manifested its own security issues, including a spike in social unrest, police brutality, and violent crime. UN Security Council (2020) observed that COVID-19 has disrupted lives and the functioning of institutions across countries that already suffer a range of serious security and development challenges.

Most importantly, Nigeria economy has taken a hammering on COVID-19. Taxes on spending, income and commodities have all plummeted. The support from multilateral agencies, led by IMF's conditionality-free facilities to tackle external shocks such as COVID-19, has not been adequate to cover the gaps created by the pandemic. The result is that worthwhile infrastructural projects, which are one of several proven routes out of underdevelopment, have often been deferred (Kronsten, 2020). The slowdown in economic activities due to COVID-19 deprives States of the resources they needed to address the socio-economic impact of the pandemic, with the risk of creating social unrest. The COVID-19 pandemic has resulted in over 2 billion people in the world being affected by lockdowns. This has significant socio-economic implications, especially in areas such as crime, where police resources are diverted from crime prevention towards enforcing lockdowns (Poblete-Cazenave, 2020). However, no criminological study has been made on the scourge of COVID-19 pandemic concerning Nigeria's security challenges but reports indicate that many countries had implemented the COVID-19 lockdown with significant cases of human rights abuses by security personnel (Africanews, 2020; Amnesty International, 2020; BBC News, 2020; Human Rights Watch, 2020; Idris, 2020; Khalid, 2020; Nigeriarights, 2020; Ojukwu, 2020; Gardaworld News, 2020a; Olurounbi, 2020). Hence, the study investigated the issues surrounding the COVID-19 lockdown as regards to the security of Nigeria.

Review of Related Literature

Daminola (2020) posited that national emergencies, like the COVID-19 pandemic, have brought along with them, security challenges. It is reasonable to admit a rise in crime rate, as idle and impoverished hoodlums, turned to crime and extortion of helpless citizens for survival. Account of the records of casualties, in security mishaps outnumbering actual deaths recorded, for the pandemic. Violating individual's rights in an attempt to enforce the law, is barbaric and should be frowned at, by the Nigerian Security Agencies. Bribery and irregularities are other major challenges of the security agencies, as exposed by the pandemic experiences. Lawal (2020) opined that the restriction of movements and closing of all businesses to curb the spread of COVID-19 have brought a scourge of hunger which is partly responsible for the recent occurrence of burglary of stores and homes, increase in violent attacks by hungry Nigerians on fellow citizens and other petty crimes in an attempt to dispossess people of food items to eat and survive. Enforcing total lockdown without complementary socio-economic palliatives as witnessed, would lead to an increase in criminality and violence especially among young people as they cannot remain indoors for a long period without food, water and electricity. CLEEN Foundation (2020) posited that Covid-19 pandemic has exacerbated sexual and gender based violence in Nigeria. Unfortunately, incidents of rape and other sexual and gender-based crimes have multiplied across the geopolitical zones in Nigeria. Nigeria Travel Advisory (2020) advised the public to reconsider traveling to Nigeria due to COVID-19, crime, terrorism, civil unrest, kidnapping, and maritime crime. Pointing out that some areas have increased risk.

United Nations (2020) suggested that the impact of COVID-19 on crime, security and the rule of law are going to be significant and long-lasting. Kishor (2020) maintained that the uninterrupted propaganda and activity of Boko Haram may affect the people of the region much more than before. He also added that it has the potential to damage the relief expected to combat COVID-19. Any health intervention by Muslims, individuals, State or international agencies during the pandemic has been viewed by Boko Haram as Haram (Forbidden). Knowing the brutality unleashed by Boko Haram in the past, Boko Haram is not just a terrorist organization killing and kidnapping people but a public health risk now. Campell (2020) also pointed out that the fall in oil prices spurred by the global response to COVID-19 has probably had a greater impact on the government's fight against jihadists. More than 60 percent of government revenue and more than 90 percent of Nigeria's foreign exchange come from oil. The catastrophic price drop over the past three months has sharply cut into government revenue. This comes at a time when the government faces heavy expenses to acquire medical equipment and set up testing facilities. With public health demands and the fall in government revenue, chronic underfunding of the security services is likely to get worse, reducing the capacity to fight jihadi's groups.

Guirakhoo (2020) posited that COVID-19-related misinformation has primarily been spread via social media and private messaging platforms. Misinformation does not always have the same tangible financial impact as other types of cyber-criminal activity, but it can still be used to cause panic, incite racism and xenophobia, and result in shortages of supplies and critical medical equipment. Guirakhoo (2020) further pointed out that COVID-19 itself presents a significant global security risk to individuals and organizations across the world, cybercriminal activity around this global pandemic can result in financial damage and promote dangerous guidance, ultimately putting additional strain on efforts to contain the virus. Madeira (2020) observed that the Nigerian military is now facing the added pressures of budget cuts and the need to police the response to COVID-19, which will weaken the already thinly stretched military's efforts to fight jihadist groups like Boko Haram/ISWAP. The difficulty in conducting proper counterterrorism operations is also coming at a time when Boko Haram/ISWAP have launched multiple attacks, the highest profile of which being a day of violence that killed more than 100 Chadian and Nigerian soldiers.

Gardaworld News (2020b) The Islamic State-affiliated faction of Boko Haram is likely to take advantage of the spread of COVID-19 and associated security precautions to step up attacks, with the aim of regaining control of large areas of the three northeastern states where the group operates. Campell (2020) posits that the Nigerian security services are struggling with a general breakdown of law and order. The pandemic and the economic consequences of fighting it have exacerbated, but did not cause the nationwide erosion of security. The Nigerian army was already overstretched before the arrival of COVID-19, with the country beset by conflict in the northeast, where Boko Haram is active. Confrontation over land and water has driven inter-communal attacks, and kidnappings and cattle-rustling operations have increased. Furthermore, the oil-producing Niger Delta remains restive. The army is stationed in nearly all of Nigeria's thirty-six states, in many cases doing the work of police forces, which are poorly trained, overstretched, and under-resourced. From the foregoing literature review, it has been established that COVID-19 pandemic and the nationwide lockdown had been a threat to Nigeria's security. Hence, a sociological theory has been employed to offer explanation to the phenomenon at hand.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The study was guided by the assumptions of Ichiro Kawachi, Bruce Kennedy and Richard Wilkinson's Social Disorganization and Relative Deprivation approach developed in 1999 (Kawachi, Kennedy and Wilkinson, 1999). They were trained in the health care field but they also ventured into the study of crime. They used social disorganization and relative deprivation approach from public health to explain crime. Using data on homicide and other categories of crime, they explored the nature of the association between income distribution, mortality and a measure of social cohesion in the United States.

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They suggested that the crime rate reflects the quality of life in a community and have reported that crime increases when social buffers that normally exist in middle-class neighborhoods disappear (Kawachi, Kennedy and Wilkinson, 1999). In application of this theory to the study, the economic downturn orchestrated by COVID-19 lockdown coupled with existing high volume of unemployment and high cost of living, created new opportunities for criminal activities with more severe crimes such as terrorism, armed robbery, rape, murder, drug trafficking, child theft, cyber-crime among others across the country. For instance, during COVID-19 lockdown, businesses were forced to close and people in informal sector that formed the majority in the business sector were unable to cater for themselves and their families throughout the period of the unexpected lockdown. These strains among those in the informal sector pushed majority into crime. Economic disadvantages increased lawlessness and other criminalities which have really affected the existing security mechanisms on ground.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted an online survey design for smart phones and tablet PCs. This survey design has speed and convenience advantages plus the ability to collect data from individuals for whom you may not have a sampling frame. To accomplish this task, software was needed and the service of a web-based survey host was sought.

Sample size of 400 was determined using Taro Yamen's scientific formula. Population of the study consisted social media users who were volunteers. The primary data was collected through a structured questionnaire schedule designed and circulated on social media platforms to get firsthand information from participants. Out of 400 copies of questionnaire circulated on social media, only 302 responded positively. Data was presented and analyzed descriptively using frequency distribution table and simple percentages. To make an informed decision about participating in the research, volunteers were briefed on (a) the general nature of the survey, especially (b) the identity of the sponsor of the research (c) how the data will be used (d) the average length of time to complete the survey, and if they will be contacted in the future with additional surveys and (e) whether any risks are involved in participating in the survey.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Table 1: Frequency distribution of responses based on study variables

Statement	Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
(1) Choose your sex	Male	180	59.60
	Female	122	40.40
	Total	302	100
(2) COVID-19 has a negative impact on the, security architecture of Nigeria.	Agreed	135	44.70
	Strongly Agreed	165	54.64
	Undecided	0	0.00
	Disagreed	1	0.33
	Strongly Disagreed	1	0.33
	Total	302	100
(3) Activities of terrorism, banditry, armed robbery, corruption, theft, extortion, human right violations, murder, fraud, cyber theft and other criminal activities were on the increase during the nationwide COVID-19 lockdown in Nigeria.	Agreed	176	58.28
	Strongly Agreed	119	39.40
	Undecided	0	0.00
	Disagreed	1	0.33
	Strongly Disagreed	6	1.99
	Total	302	100
(4) Government gives more attention to fighting COVID-19 than Boko Haram, farmers-herdsmen conflict, banditry, armed robbery, etc	Agreed	100	33.11
	Strongly Agreed	144	47.68
	Undecided	3	0.99
	Disagreed	24	7.95
	Strongly Disagreed	31	10.26
	Total	302	100
(5) The economic hardship from the restriction of movement to avoid the spread of COVID-19 in Nigeria forced many people in the informal sector to commit crimes.	Agreed	153	50.66
	Strongly Agreed	145	48.01
	Undecided	0	0.00
	Disagreed	1	0.33
	Strongly Disagreed	3	0.99
	Total	302	100
(6) There were series of complains concerning financial extortion among the security personnel who were deployed to enforce the nationwide COVID-19 lockdown.	Agreed	150	49.67
	Strongly Agreed	152	50.33
	Undecided	0	0.00
	Disagreed	0	0.00
	Strongly Disagreed	0	0.00
	Total	302	100
(7) During COVID-19 lockdown human rights violation by security personnel mostly the Nigeria Police Force was enormous.	Agreed	155	51.32
	Strongly Agreed	144	47.68
	Undecided	0	0.00
	Disagreed	2	0.66
	Strongly Disagreed	1	0.33
	Total	302	100
(8) COVID-19 palliatives by Federal and State Governments benefitted the few while the poor masses were on the disadvantaged condition.	Agreed	167	55.30
	Strongly Agreed	111	36.75
	Undecided	5	1.66
	Disagreed	7	2.32
	Strongly Disagreed	12	3.97
	Total	302	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2020

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Table 1 showed that 180 male representing 59.60% and 122 female representing 40.40% took part in the study. This implies that male respondents dominated the study population. The result is in line with Ritchie and Roser (2019) who concluded that “in all countries, there are more male than female births”. This means that all else being equal, we would expect males to account for slightly more than half of the total population. On average, women live longer than men and this is true for every country in the world (Ritchie and Roser, 2019). Study result indicated that 135 respondents representing 44.70% agreed that COVID-19 has a negative impact on the security of Nigeria. More so, 165 respondents representing 54.64% strongly agreed to that opinion while those who chose disagreed and strongly disagreed had 1 each representing 0.66% (see table 2, statement 2). It therefore means that majority of respondents were of the opinion that COVID-19 has a negative impact on the security of Nigeria.

Study result shows that 176 respondents representing 58.28% agreed that activities of terrorism, corruption, street theft, banditry, extortion, human rights violation, murder, internet fraud, and other criminal activities were on the increase during the nationwide COVID-19 lockdown in Nigeria. To confirm this opinion, 119 respondents representing 39.40% strongly agreed. Only 1 respondent representing 0.33% disagreed while 6 respondents representing 1.99% strongly disagreed (see table 2, statement 3). Based on the popular opinion given, it therefore means that activities of terrorism, corruption, street theft, banditry, extortion, human rights violation, murder, internet fraud, and other criminal activities were on the increase during the nationwide COVID-19 lockdown in Nigeria. Another popular opinion shows that government has given more attention to fighting COVID-19 than Boko Haram, farmers-herdsmen conflict, banditry, armed robbery, etc. Those who agreed to this opinion were 100 respondents representing 33.11%, strongly agreed were 144 respondents representing 47.68%, 3 respondents representing 0.99% were undecided, 24 respondents representing 7.95% disagreed while 31 respondents representing 10.26% strongly disagreed (see table 2, statement 4). The statistics here shows that Nigeria government has given priority in the fight against COVID-19 than Boko Haram, farmers-herdsmen conflict, banditry, armed robbery, etc. No wonder President Muhammadu Buhari in his statement on 13th April, 2020 said “In Nigeria, we are taking two steps approaches. First, to protect the lives of our fellow Nigerians and residents living here, and second, to preserve the livelihoods of workers and business owners”. This does not mean that government has totally abandoned or forgotten about the fight against terrorism and other criminal activities in the country but to give urgent attention to health issue that ravaged the whole world. To prove it further, the Northern Governors Forum (NGF) through the chairman and Plateau State Governor, Simon Lalong on 21st May, 2020 expressed his concern over the infection rates of COVID-19 across the region, which had further exacerbated by incidents of violent and deadly crime across some states including terrorist violence in Borno, banditry in Katsina and other areas. He therefore, acknowledged and appreciated the intervention of the federal government following their request to President Muhammadu Buhari for the deployment of more security personnel to the region to tackle banditry, kidnapping, insurgency, and other crimes which are threatening livelihoods and preventing farmers from going to their farms.

Result of the study indicated that the economic hardship caused by the restriction of movement to avoid the further spread of COVID-19 in Nigeria has forced many people in the informal sectors to commit heinous crimes. This opinion was confirmed by 153 respondents representing 50.66% with agreed responses, 145 respondents representing 48.01% strongly agreed, 1 respondent representing 0.33% disagreed while those who strongly disagreed to this opinion were 3 respondents representing 0.99% (see table 2, statement 5). Study reveals that there were series of complaints concerning financial extortion among the security personnel who were deployed to enforce the nationwide COVID-19 lockdown. This opinion has been agreed by 150 respondents representing 49.67% while 152 respondents representing 50.33% strongly agreed (see table 2, statement 6).

It was also revealed in the study that during the COVID-19 lockdown, human rights violation by security personnel mostly by the Nigeria Police Force was enormous.

A popular opinion with 155 respondents representing 51.32% agreed and 144 respondents representing 47.68% strongly agreed. In a counter opinion, 2 respondents representing 0.66% disagreed while 1 respondent representing 0.33% strongly disagreed (see table 2, statement 7).

Result of the study also revealed that 167 respondents representing 55.30% agreed that COVID-19 palliatives by Federal and State Governments benefitted the few while the poor masses were disadvantaged in the distribution, 111 respondents representing 36.75% strongly agreed, 5 respondents representing 1.66% were undecided, 7 respondents representing 2.32% disagreed while 12 respondents representing 3.97% strongly disagreed (see table 2, statement 8). Majority opinion survey shows that COVID-19 palliatives by Federal and State Governments benefitted the few while the poor masses were on their disadvantaged condition and this could be the reason some people took to crime for survival.

FINDINGS

The outbreak of COVID-19 in Nigeria has assumed a frightening dimension owing to increase in criminal activities and general insecurity. Nigerians experienced wide range of human, social, environmental and economic security issues. While it may be posited that COVID-19 is a global problem, it is as well a serious burden to the existing insecurity challenges in the country.

From the presentation of data analysis, the following findings were made:

- i COVID-19 has a negative impact on the security of Nigeria.
- ii Activities of terrorism, corruption, street theft, banditry, extortion, human rights violation, murder, internet fraud, and other criminal activities were on the increase during the nationwide COVID-19 lockdown in Nigeria.
- iii Government has given more attention to fighting COVID-19 than Boko Haram, farmers-herdsmen conflict, banditry, armed robbery, etc.
- iv. The economic hardship caused by the restriction of movement to avoid the further spread of COVID-19 in Nigeria has forced many people in the informal sectors to commit heinous crimes.
- v There were series of complaints concerning financial extortion among the security personnel who were deployed to enforce the nationwide COVID-19 lockdown.
- vii During the COVID-19 lockdown, human rights violation by security personnel mostly by the Nigeria Police Force were higher than before.
- vii COVID-19 palliatives by Federal and State Governments benefitted the few while the poor masses were on their disadvantaged condition and this could be the reason some people took to crime for survival.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Study of the findings had shown that COVID-19 has a negative impact on the security of Nigeria. This is supported by Asimi (2020) and United Nations (2020) who were of the opinion that amidst the COVID-19 pandemic, terrorism, street crime, online crime, illegal drug markets and smuggling, human and wildlife trafficking, slavery, robberies and burglaries were on the rise. With more people spending more time online, cyber-crime has increased through the sale of fake medical products online and requesting for bank details to access federal government palliatives. The World Health Organization published a cyber-security notice, warning people of fraudsters imitating WHO employees (WHO, 2020).

The National Human Rights Commission reported that security agents had killed 18 people in the first two weeks of the lockdown. This was more than the number of national COVID-19 fatalities at that time. The report noted that the excessive use of force by the security personnel deployed to different locations to enforce the nationwide lockdown, created more fear among the citizenry than the dread of COVID-19.. Although inter-agency cooperation between the police and other institutions increased as a result of the COVID-19 lockdown, enforcement of the lock-down also amplified existing challenges around human rights abuses and bureaucratic corruption within the state institutions.

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The police and the military have also been accused of extortion by taking bribes from motorists in exchange for free passage at checkpoints. Social Development Integrated Centre (2020) reported that on Friday, the 17th of April 2020, officers of the Nigerian Police force extorted the sum of N120,000 from Mrs Nwabuabo Obiajulu and her son Chukwunweike for flouting the lockdown directive in Delta state. There was incidence of Taskforce members beating up commercial drivers, engaging in street fights, impounding vehicles even without notifying the owners of the vehicle their offences. Regrettably, the enforcement measure was taken by some unpatriotic staff and officers within the Nigeria security agencies that perpetuated severe human rights abuses on some Nigerians. These abuses include physical assault, torture, illegal seizure, extortions and incidences of sexual and gender-based violence. Furthermore, there were cases of outright destruction of property by security agents, thus inflicting hardship and pains on the vulnerable citizens, especially women and youths. It is unfortunate to note that, in some cases, such abuses have resulted in deaths. According to reports, such brutalities by security operatives in places like Abia, Anambra, Delta, Kaduna, Niger, Ebonyi and Katsina States kills 18 people while COVID-19 killed 12 within the same period (Africa News, 2020). These unacceptable incidents are attributed to the undesired work of overzealous security agents in enforcing the lockdown. In Port Harcourt, a female Police Officer met her untimely death on Thursday 23rd, April 2020, after she was shot dead by a colleague, Sergeant Bitrus Osaiah while trying to enforce movement restriction put in place by the Rivers State government to curb the spread of COVID-19 (Social Development Integrated Centre (2020)).

The restriction of movement to avoid the further spread of COVID-19 in Nigeria forced many people mostly those in the informal sector to commit heinous crimes. The vast majority of people outside of the formal system were devastatingly affected by the lockdown. The disruption to their daily livelihood had a huge and significant impact on their ability to meet their most basic needs; hence, they resort to crime. The informal sector, in which more than 80% of Nigerians work, includes a wide range of occupations, from street traders, taxi drivers, tradesmen, and artisans to food vendors and hairdressers. In Lagos alone, with an estimated population of 25 million people, 42 percent of business activities are found in the informal sector and 65% of people work in the informal sector. Informal workers have lower incomes; often do not have savings, health insurance, or pensions that provide a basic social safety net. This is supported by Obiakor (2020) who observed that people in this population belong to the category of people who are most vulnerable to the negative economic shocks surrounding the COVID-19 pandemic. Their income generating activities are more closely tied to the daily whims of the market. Furthermore, for this category of people, their ability to meet their immediate basic needs such as access to food, shelter and health services, predicated on daily access to face-to-face interactions and customer flow. Some micro entrepreneurs were trapped with the repayment and high interest loans associated with predatory loans; this is especially pertinent for women who are often the target and recipients of micro loans. Households with some savings, some were overburdened (because a large proportion of the population is dependent on a large workforce), and for others, the persistence of the lockdown beyond the expected period forced many of them into a precarious situation, that exposed them to committing petty crimes like theft to sustain their livelihood.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

From the foregoing analysis, the findings show that COVID-19 has impacted negatively on the security architecture of Nigeria. Enforcement of nationwide COVID-19 lockdown had recorded series of human rights abuses by security personnel, most especially among the Nigeria Police Force, Nigeria Army and other security agents, which include physical assault, torture, illegal seizure, extortions and incidences of sexual and gender-based violence. It was also evidenced in the study that the restriction of movement ordered to avoid the spread of COVID-19 in Nigeria had affected many people mostly those in the informal sector and this has contributed in no mean measure, on why some of them went into committing heinous crimes.

In sum, the lockdowns and curfew enforcements in Nigeria was significantly lawful, to the extent that it was covered in the constitution. For instance, Section 305(1, 3a, 3b, 3c) of the Nigerian Constitution, 1999, gives government the rights to declare curfew in emergencies or when there is enormous threat to national security to citizens. This also agrees with the 1985 International Commission of Jurists' Siracusa Principles. Some Countries hid under these local and international laws to declare covid-19 lockdowns and curfews, since WHO (2020) declared the pandemic a global emergency. The COVID-19 lockdown was used discriminatively against disadvantaged and vulnerable groups across the states in Nigeria. Those who could not give bribe to the COVID-19 enforcement officers, mainly the poor people, were brutalized, detained overnight on the road and many were forced to cut large portion of grasses by the roadside.

Based on the outcome of this analysis, we hereby make the following recommendations:

- i. The attention given to fighting COVID-19 should be given to security of life and property in Nigeria.
- ii. Government of Nigeria should not allow the security agents to abandon their constitutional duties as a result of COVID-19 pandemic.
- iii. Finally, there is need for government to fight COVID-19 and insecurity respectively. However, both needs sincerity of purpose, such would go a long way in solving the current challenges in the country.
- iv. There should be concerted effort in the training and retraining of security agents in Nigeria. This would help in improving their impact on society and avoid internal corruption.

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